

Sand erosion behavior of GFRP

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ABSTRACT

Sand erosion tests were made with glass cloth/polyester composites and polyester resin by using the sand blasting type erosion tester in which the solid glass particle was accelerated by flowing air and impinged to the plate specimen. Impact velocity of particles was varied from 13 to 60 m/s and attack angle was varied from 20 to 90 deg..

The change of weight loss with time at 90 deg. of glass composites showed multi erosion stages. In each stage, these composed two lines with different slopes. Lower slope was obtained in the period of matrix damage, and higher slope was of glass cloth. This behavior is different from that of homogeneous materials such as resins and metals. In volume erosion rate, at higher angle attack resin showed good resistance to erosion damage but at lower attack angle glass composites shows good resistance. The method to estimate the erosion rate of glass composite at 90 deg. impact was proposed, and the calculated value agreed well with the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Sand erosion; Fiber, glass; Glass cloth
Matrix, polyester

1.INTRODUCTION

Thermosetting composites, have been replacing metals and widely used in the aerospace, transportation and chemical industries, because of their high specific strength and good corrosion resistance.

Erosive phenomena, materials removal by impact of solid particles, have been a serious problem in many industries, then it was discussed and

reviewed by many researchers on homogeneous materials such as metals and plastics^{1,2)}. However, the erosion behavior of the composites has been received much less attention than that of conventional materials^{3,4)}.

In this paper, the sand erosion characteristics of the glass cloth composites was investigated and also the method to estimate the erosion rate was discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Sand blast type erosion apparatus is shown in Fig.1. The compressed air at room temperature is mixed with the glass powders with diameter of 350 μ m and the two phase flow is accelerated in the ejector, and then this flow impinges the test specimen placed 2 cm away from the nozzle tip. Weight change was measured after testing by a balance with a sensitivity of 0.01 mg.

The impact velocity of glass powders was controlled by changing an amount of flowing air and measured with the rotating disk technique⁵⁾. Impact velocity of glass particles was varied from 13 to 60 m/s and angle of attack was varied from 20 to 90 deg..

The materials tested were unsaturated polyester resin and its fibrous composites. Glass contents of composites were varied from 0(resin) to 50 wt.%. And the special test specimen containing only one ply glass cloth was also tested.

3. RESULTS

Fig.2 shows the typical example of weight loss with time for composites(40 wt.%) and resin specimens, at particle velocity(V_p) of 25.0 m/s and attack angle of 90 deg.. In this figure, cumulative erosion is plotted against the weight of particles impinged. At 90 deg., erosion curve of glass composites is composed of many stages and each one has high and low two different slopes. Eroded surfaces in each period are shown in Fig.3. Damaged layer of only matrix(a) or glass cloth surface(b) are recognized, and lower slope stage is obtained in the damage period for resin matrix and higher one is that of glass cloth respectively. This suggests the erosion damage of glass composites proceeds by removing resin layer and glass cloth layer alternatively. Actually the lower slopes in erosion curve of glass composites(Fig.2) coincides with that of resin(●). This behavior was observed in all experimental conditions, at higher attack angle, and was different from that of homogeneous materials such as resin. The erosion curve at lower attack angle, for example at 35 deg., is shown in Fig.4. At lower attack angle, multi stage damage behavior can be

recognized only in initial stage. In the latter stage, those two stages are indistinct and showed linearity because at these angles some matrix layers or glass clothes are eroded in the same time. The erosion rates are calculated as an average slope of the cumulative erosion-time curve after the first period of surface resin erosion. For attack angle of 90 deg. the average erosion rate is given by broken line as shown in Fig.2 and for lower attack angle, for example at 35 deg., the average erosion rate is given by the stationary line begins from the point "Mt" in Fig.4. In calculation of erosion rate, the damage period of surface resin layer is ignored, because the thickness of this resin layer is affected by glass contents.

Fig.5 shows the average erosion rates of the materials at various attack angles and the velocity of 25.0 m/s. Then average erosion rate of resin shows maximum value at nearly 30 deg.. This behavior is similar to that of ductile materials as metals which are easily eroded by cutting by glancing impact. However erosion rate of glass composites, the peak of erosion rate exists at nearly or over 60 deg.. As glass contents become higher, the erosion rate peak approaches to 90 deg.. This behavior is similar to that of brittle materials such as glass which are easily eroded with cracks by repeated impact. From these results, it was found that the erosion behavior showed more and more brittleness by reinforcing resin with glass cloth. In the view point of designing, the volume erosion rate is more important than erosion rate based on weight loss shown in previous figures. Volume erosion rate of resin and 50 wt.% specimen are shown in Fig.6. At higher attack angle resin showed good resistance to erosion damage in comparison with composites, but at lower attack angle glass composites shows good resistance to erosion damage. So, in case of using the FRP member the attack angle of the particles in the circumstances should be considered.

4. DISCUSSION

The erosion process can be separated perfectly into the damage of matrix and glass cloth layer especially at attack angle of 90 deg.. So, in Fig.2 the damage of glass cloth layer begins at point A, and the matrix layer is damaged successively in period B-C. Then average erosion rate is estimated by using the slope between A-B-C, and Wf' . The Wf' means the weight fraction of cloth layer containing glass and resin. To determine the erosion rate of cloth layer (slope of line A-B), erosion test was carried out with using one-ply glass cloth specimen. Fig.7 shows a test result of one ply specimen at $V_p = 25.0$ m/s for 90 deg. impact. The ero-

sion rate of cloth layer can be obtained from the slope of straight line D-E. The erosion rate of glass composites is able to estimate by Eq.(1)

$$E_c = \frac{E_f \cdot E_m}{(1 - W_f') \cdot E_f + W_f' \cdot E_m} \quad (1)$$

where E_c is erosion rate of glass cloth composites, E_m is that of matrix layer obtained from the erosion curve of resin itself and E_f is that of glass cloth layer obtained by one ply specimen. And W_f' was determined by optical microscopic method. In Fig.8, experimental results and calculated values of E_c are plotted against weight fraction of cloth layer at various velocities for 90 deg. impact. In this figure test results showed good agreement with calculated values.

5. CONCLUSIONS

(1) The erosion curve of the composites at normal attack angle showed two slopes, and lower slope was obtained in the period of matrix damage, and higher slope was of glass cloth. This sand erosion behavior of glass cloth composites obtained different from that of homogeneous materials.

(2) Glass composites showed brittle behavior in erosion compared with the resin, and this behavior was emphasized with an increase of glass contents.

(3) Glass composites showed superiority in lower attack angle but at higher attack angle contrary results are obtained.

(4) The equation to estimate the erosion rate of glass cloth composites was proposed.

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Fig.1 Schematic diagram of experimental apparatus.

Fig.2 Typical erosion-time curve at high attack angle for resin and composites.

Fig.3 Optical observations of eroded surfaces of GFRP: (a)matrix layer and (b)glass cloth layer.

Fig.4 Typical erosion-time curve at low attack angle for resin and composites.

Fig.5 Effect of attack angle on erosion rate of various glass contents.

Fig.6 Effect of attack angle on volume erosion rate of resin and 50 wt.% GFRP.

Fig.7 Typical erosion-time curve of only one ply specimen at 90 deg..

Fig.8 Comparison of experimental and calculated erosion rate at various impact velocities.(Solid line; calculated value.)